

FORMATION OF TRADITIONAL TRADE FACILITIES IN HISTORICAL URBAN CENTERS ON THE PRINCIPLES OF DESIGN -CODE

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ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ ТРАДИЦИОННЫХ ТОРГОВЫХ ОБЪЕКТОВ В ИСТОРИЧЕСКИХ ЦЕНТРАХ ГОРОДОВ НА ОСНОВЕ ПРИНЦИПОВ ДИЗАЙН-КОДА

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Annotatsiya. Zamon talabi bo'lmish hozrgi davr hayotida tarixiy shaharlarning ko'rinishi va unda saqlangan obidalar, meroslarni kelajak avlodga yetkazish eng asosiy masalalar qatorida. Mazkur maqolada tarixiy shaharlarning savdo obyektlarida mavjud muammolar va dizayn kod tamoyillarini shakllantirish va amalda qo'llashga bo'lgan ehtiyoj masalasi yoritilgan. Aynan ushbu dizayn kodlarni tarixiy shahar savdo obyektlarida madaniy va etnik xususiyatlarini hisobga olgan holda qo'llash tashrif buyuruvchilar va savdo ishlari uchun ko'plab qulayliklar yaratadi ularni oqimini oshirishda hizmat qiladi, shaharning muhitining sifatini yaxshilashga va eng asosiy tamoyillaridan biri, hozrda dolzarb yo'nalishlardan bo'lgan tanlangan markazning savdo-reklama faoliyatini rivojlantiradi.

Аннотация. В жизни современности, которая является требованием времени, появление исторических городов и памятников, хранящихся в них, передача наследия будущим поколениям являются одними из основных вопросов. В данной статье освещаются существующие проблемы и необходимость формирования и практического применения принципов кодекса проектирования в торговых объектах исторических городов. Именно применение этих проектных кодексов в исторических городских торговых объектах с учетом их культурных и этнических особенностей создает множество удобств для посетителей и торговых предприятий, служит для увеличения их потока, способствует улучшению качества городской среды и развитию торгово-рекламной деятельности выбранного центра, одним из основных принципов которой является актуальность в настоящее время.

Abstract. The appearance of historical cities and the monuments preserved in it, the transmission of heritage to the future generation are among the most fundamental issues in the life of the modern demand hozrgi period. This article covers the existing problems in the commercial facilities of historical cities and the question of the need to formulate and apply the principles of the design code in practice. It is the application of these design codes taking into account their cultural and ethnic characteristics in historical urban commercial facilities that creates many facilities for visitors and commercial work that will serve them in increasing their flow, improving

the quality of the city's environment and developing one of the most basic principles, the commercial and promotional activities of the selected center, which

Kalit so'zlar: tarixiy shahar, dizayn-kod, statsionar, nostatsionar, reklama, visual shovqin

Ключевые слова: исторический город, дизайн-код, стационарный, нестационарный, рекламный, визуальный шум

Keywords: historical city, design-code, stationary, non-stationary, advertising, visual noise

Enter. The attractiveness of a region is a key factor in choosing tourist destinations. The most important way to increase the tourist attractiveness of a resort is to create a comfortable urban environment. The digital environment of the centre, created through photo and video materials, contributes to the comfortable appearance of the travel destination and the city, and improves its quality. Therefore, state regulation of reforms in the development of tourism should not only support the tourism industry and infrastructure organisations, but also contribute to the creation of a comfortable urban environment.

At this point, it should be said that the principles of the design code have not yet been fully developed in Uzbekistan in terms of requirements and laws. In order to attract the attention of customers, various organisations used unregulated combinations of symbols, shapes, colours that cause discomfort, in a word, advertisements that cause visual noise. But sometimes organisations do this work taking into account the wishes and requirements of customers, as a result of which the rules of the established directions of functionality are violated. In order to prevent and eliminate these problems and issues, we will be able to observe that significant changes in the environment will occur if the laws, regulations and proposals established by the state are put into force.

As an example, we can consider the strategy for the rapid and innovative development of the construction network of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2021-2025, as per the decree of the President of Uzbekistan No. 6119 of 27.11.2020. According to the strategy, by 2025 it was decided to cover all the cities of Uzbekistan and 25% of urban settlements with master plans. It was established that public opinion will be taken into account when approving the master plans. By July 1, 2022, a regional "design code" will be developed and implemented, taking into account the purpose of the elements of the urban environment, traditional architecture and culture, as well as the natural and climatic conditions of the place [1].

Tashkent has long been known as a centre engaged in trade and commerce. Historical sources show that in ancient times there were large bazaars in the city of Shosh. Due to the location of the city on the Great Silk Road, in the past there was trade with foreign countries through caravans. Currently, there are more than 10 markets in the city of Tashkent [2].

The development and implementation of the design code helps to create an easily recognizable and unique city brand, stimulates the development of the city, increases the flow of tourists, and increases the social capitalization of the city and its inhabitants [3].

In terms of service, we divide trade objects into two types: stationary and non-stationary trade objects. A stationary commercial object is a building and structure or an object located in a part of it. A non-stationary trade object is a temporary structure object that is not firmly connected to the land plot, including temporary retail trade objects that are not technologically connected to networks of engineering structures. They are buildings and structures that are not firmly attached to the ground no higher than one floor, and which allow for free movement or dismantling and

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subsequent assembly without damaging or changing their structural characteristics as a result of changing the space [5].

Stationary and Nonstationary of objects difference	Criterion		
	Plot of land contact with	Communal connect to networks	Register the property transfer
Stationary commercial objects	With foundation and ground there is a strong connection	In many cases it is connected	By the state will be registered
Nonstationary commercial objects	There is no solid connection	Not necessarily	Just a contract confirms the rights

1- application

The historic-cultural urban environment should be considered a shared resource and society must be prepared to examine and accept different versions of future development, combining practical and conceptual thinking [4].

The design code addresses the following tasks:

- removes visual clutter from the city (comical signs, building facades with excessive ornamentation, absurd non-capital structures, etc.);
- helps to attract more pedestrians to the streets, which in turn benefits small businesses;
- increases the city's appeal to tourists;
- improves environmental quality;
- helps to preserve the architectural and historical value of the location;
- enhances street safety through appropriate infrastructure and lighting [6].

Legal, financial and administrative measures are implemented to protect and maintain the condition and appearance of the city through the design code, including establishing rules and requirements for the management of heritage zones and their suburbs, and adopting laws with penalties for violations. Problems are overcome by providing guidelines on the design and colours of commercial signs within the framework of design and design codes [7].

«Optimal» design code creation process

2- application

The applications below provide general examples of historic city views for design code examples. In the market of the entire Uzbek region, mainly the city of Tashkent; to be more precise, we can see it in the example of the Eskishahar area. Based on the principles of the design code, commercial objects are illuminated as a proposal in terms of their colour, style, shape and size, carried out, illuminated and restored within the same category.

Ancient map of the Old City

The predecessor of the Old Town and current appearances

3- application

4- application

Many commercial facilities and markets were present in old city areas, and while the markets have been preserved, most residential areas and former streets have lost their historical appearance. The proposed project aims to apply design code principles to commercial structures not just in one market but across all commercial complexes in the Old City. This is because many commercial structures have become dispersed, with modern buildings replacing historical streets and residential homes between commercial complexes. Understanding the primary aesthetic elements of urban shopping streets is critical. Proper planning of buildings and their components in cities reduces environmental impact and improves the surroundings [8].

**Design code principles of historical cities
proposal project for commercial objects**

5- application

Implementation of legal, financial, and administrative measures for the protection and preservation of the district, including the establishment of regulations and requirements for the management of heritage zones and their suburbs, the adoption of laws with penalties for violations,

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and the design of commercial signs within the framework of design codes and colors are eliminated by providing instructions. Accordingly:

- Solving the issue of street vendors by removing illegal occupations in commercial facilities while providing alternative locations for vendors.
- Improve the visual appeal of the street through the following strategies:
 - Using structural elements to create a cohesive look while maintaining consistency throughout the design process, which reinforces a sense of unity and establishes a visual rhythm. Emphasizes the uniqueness of the historic district to foster a sense of belonging among citizens and emphasize the unique character and personality of the area.
 - To strengthen the identity of the place, to demonstrate its urban diversity and harmony, through banners and advertisements that preserve the decoration of the design that reflects the social values and spatial characteristics of the area.
 - Adding green spaces to urban areas within commercial areas to mitigate environmental pollution from activity and human concentration.
 - Create a touristic commercial route that offers a range of activities and helps establish attractions”

The placement of non-stationary trade objects in the city area is carried out in accordance with the zoning scheme for the placement of non-stationary trade objects, taking into account the need to ensure the sustainable development of the territories, including: It is possible to provide commercial objects with a minimum area.

Non-stationary trade objects

6- application

The growth indicators of all sectors are currently increasing to a certain extent in the state of Uzbekistan. In particular, we are witnessing a lot of work being done in the field of architecture and design. However, it is worth noting that in most parts of the development of city buildings, we can find similarities in appearance and structure of public and residential buildings at every step. However, by changing these stereotypes, we can create projects that have an unusual look and type

in a modular system, using pieces of regional national ornament. Taking into account these issues, it is possible to create a solution by making the commercial objects located on the streets look like stylized national ornaments of the region through the module system. Modular design or "modularity in design" is a design approach that breaks down a system into smaller parts that can be created independently and then used in different systems.

Based on regional ornament stylization sketches of modular commercial objects

7- application

A module is a functional system that can be extended and reused. It offers flexibility in design and reduces costs. The modular approach allows any module to be replaced or added to the rest of the system without affecting the overall aesthetic. Furthermore, the use of a modular system for any purpose greatly expands the possibilities for choosing design forms in unique and innovative ways. A module is a system organised by proportions, with the architectural form based on the relationship between each part and the elements that compose it. These proportions are not arbitrary, but are determined by the function of the object and its location, design and materials, the aesthetic preferences of the period and the author, and the dimensions and silhouette of the object.

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